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**A NEW PARADIGM FOR THE STUDY OF NOVEL:
NOTES ON SECOND VOLUME OF THE CHINESE THIRD EDITION
COLLECTED WORKS OF MIKHAIL BAKHTIN**

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Favourably invited by Mr. Qian Zhongwen, the chief editor of the Chinese new edition *Collected Works of Mikhail Bakhtin*, the author of this paper was entrusted to write a “Translator’s Preface” for its second volume (the volume on novel theory). The present notes first briefly introduce the reception of Bakhtin’s collected works in China as well as the academic background underpinning the writing of the “Translator’s Preface”, and then with the Chinese position interpret the characteristics of Bakhtin’s study of novel theory from three perspectives: new routes, new concepts, and new paradigm.

Keywords: the Chinese-language *Collected Works of Mikhail Bakhtin*; novel theory; open theoretical system; cross-cultural dialogue; “harmony without uniformity”

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1.

In 1998, the 6-volume Chinese edition of *The Complete Works of Mikhail Bakhtin* was published [3], sparking a warm response in the Chinese academic community and creating a scene of “Luoyang paper being in short supply” (洛阳纸贵 – a phrase indicating extremely high popularity). As “the Bakhtin Boom” was waning in the Western countries, *The Complete Works* was revised and expanded to seven volumes and re-published in 2009 [4]. Mr. Qian Zhongwen, born in 1932, is the chief editor of *The Complete Works* and has long been engaged in the study of literary theory. Compared with what happened in the Western countries, Bakhtin studies in China were disadvantaged by a relatively late start, but they were to enjoy a strong momentum. Translating Bakhtin’s academic heritage is a verification of Qian Zhongwen’s sharp scholarly vision and insightful theoretical foresight.

During the summer vacation in 2017, the author of the present notes, favoured by Mr. Qian, was entrusted to write a translator’s preface for the second volume (on novel theory) of the future third edition. The first draft of this preface was completed in April 2018. The new edition of the collected works was supposed to be published by the end of 2019. However, due to non-academic factors, the publishing house canceled the publication plan. The chief editor had to change the publishing house temporarily. Coincidentally, the COVID-19 pandemic broke out at that time. The publication of the 8-volume *Collected Works of Mikhail Bakhtin* (six volumes of Bakhtin’s works and two volumes of “the disputed texts” as “appendix volumes”) was postponed further again, and it was not until August 2024 that it was finally published [5].

During the late spring and early summer of 2021, Qian reached an agreement on the publication contract with Shaanxi Normal University Press. In a letter dated July 5th, regarding the delivery of all the manuscripts of the new *Collected Works of Mikhail Bakhtin* to the press, he said, “Dear Professor Ling, thank you for your generous promise. Please send me the supplementary annotation to *On the Educational Novel* around July 7th or 8th. Your contribution has been such a timely rescue before the revised manuscript of *The Collected Works of Mikhail Bakhtin* is sent out, fulfilling everyone's expectations and my own wish of many years. In the last few days, I have been proofreading my own collected works, the pre-printing versions of volumes 3, 4, and 5. I need to make some minor changes in some places so that I would leave no regrets behind. At my age, if still favored by luck and good health this year, I may be able to see my own five-volume collected works published in time. As for the new *The Collected Works of Mikhail Bakhtin*, I can hardly expect the same. But even so I'd have no regrets! Wish you a pleasant summer!” Later on, I was told that Mr. Qian was being hospitalized for quite a period of time. Fortunately, the old man survived the pandemic. He personally checked through the final proofs of *The Collected Works of Mikhail Bakhtin* and was sent the sample books. As his juniors, we deeply admire Mr. Qian Zhongwen's magnanimous mind and spirit of perseverance in his academic pursuits. Although an article specifically commenting on his contributions to Bakhtin studies in China was published in Russia June 2025 [8], we would like to take this opportunity to sincerely wish him good health and the ever-greenness of his academic achievements!

According to the copyright system in China, there is a time requirement for the republication of academic works, usually with an interval of ten years between editions, but reprinting is not restricted. The Chinese version of *The Collected Works of Mikhail Bakhtin* has been published in three editions within 30 years, which fully demonstrates that Bakhtin's academic heritage is widely popular in the Chinese academic community. By 2011, *Problems of Dostoevsky's Poetics*, translated into Chinese by professors Bai Chunren and Gu Yaling from Beijing Foreign Studies University in 1988, ranked the eighth on the list of “Foreign Works Most Cited in Foreign Literature Theses”, while the first-edition of *The Complete Works of Mikhail Bakhtin* in 1998 ranked the first on the list of “Foreign Works Most Cited in Foreign Literature Theses” and the fourth on the list of “Foreign Works Most Cited in Chinese Literature Theses” [10, pp. 317, 289]. Qian Zhongwen wrote a “Chief Editor's Preface” for each edition, introducing in detail Bakhtin's life, his academic achievements, and the topical issues in Bakhtin studies. For this new edition, he designated “Translator's Prefaces” to be written for Volume 1 and Volume 2. As for the other volumes, “Translator's Prefaces” are not required, for which there is no obvious reason. Perhaps it is his deliberate arrangement to reserve the special honor of the “Translator's Preface” for the fourth edition. At chief editor's suggestion, the length of the translator's preface should be constrained within 8,000-9,000 Chinese characters, mainly introducing the origin and development of the volume, and highlighting the interpretive perspectives and stances of Chinese scholars. In order to be fully ready for this preface, the author of this article has successively completed three papers on Bakhtin studies in advance. The first paper, “The Forms of Poetics and the Demands of Philosophy: The Academic Achievements of Bakhtin's Novel Theory”, mainly introduces Bakhtin's academic interests from the 1930s to the early 1940s, especially the influence of “Bakhtin's Novel Theory” on the Western academic community after the publication of the English *The Dialogic Imagination: Four Essays by Mikhail Bakhtin*. The second paper, “Bakhtin's Novel Theory: Background, Clues and Characteristics”, mainly clarifies the causes and consequences of Bakhtin's research of the novel genre and the important position of his novel theory in his entire academic heritage. The third paper, “The Artistry of the Novel: Rethinking the Sources of Bakhtin's Poetics”,

examines the internal and external academic contexts of his study of novel theory, and proves the view that even without a high-pressure ideological environment, studying the aesthetic laws of novel creation, which conforms to Bakhtin's own academic interests and internal theoretical logic, would surely have become an irresistible choice for him.

2.

From the early 1980s when Bakhtin was introduced into the Chinese academic community through Dostoevsky studies and English and French literary criticism to the successive publication of three editions of *The Collected Works of Mikhail Bakhtin*, the reception of Mikhail Bakhtin in China has spanned nearly 45 years. Over those four and half decades, many works of Western literary theory of the 20th century have been introduced or translated into Chinese. These include works on Western Marxism, feminism, post-modernism, especially those of Anglo-American New Criticism, French post-structuralism, German reception aesthetics and hermeneutics, the American deconstructionist school, as well as works on performance studies and world literature studies, which have all been translated into Chinese. Of course, the works of the Russian Formalist school and the Moscow – Tartu structuralist historical – cultural semiotic school have also attracted a good deal of attention. However, to one's surprise, the above mentioned Western works have left a legacy far less enduring than those of Bakhtin's in China. How so? The key lies in the fact that Bakhtin's academic thought bears uncanny genetic resemblance to the traditional Chinese culture.

From the theoretical thoughts of the pre-Qin philosophers to Wang Yangming's theory of the mind in the late Ming Dynasty, ancient Chinese thinkers all pursued a systematic understanding of the world, and most of these understandings were closely associated with “life-orientedness”. Specifically, they were closely related to the moral pursuit at three different levels, in ascending order of importance and magnitude, of the individual, of the family and of society. The Confucian classic *The Great Learning* states: “Those in ancient times who wished to illustrate illustrious virtue throughout the world first ordered well their own states. Wishing to order well their states, they first regulated their families. Wishing to regulate their families, they first cultivated their persons. Wishing to cultivate their persons, they first rectified their hearts. Wishing to rectify their hearts, they first sought to be sincere in their thoughts. Wishing to be sincere in their thoughts, they first extended their knowledge. Such extension of knowledge lay in the investigation of things. Things being investigated, knowledge became complete. Their knowledge being complete, their thoughts were sincere. Their thoughts being sincere, their hearts were then rectified. Their hearts being rectified, their persons were cultivated. Their persons being cultivated, their families were regulated. Their families being regulated, their states were rightly governed. Their states being rightly governed, the whole world was made peaceful and happy.” The main task of self – cultivation is moral cultivation, which starts from the investigation of things and the attainment of knowledge, and is accomplished through sincerity of thought and rectification of the heart. Only those who integrate knowledge and virtue can manage their families well, and those who can manage their families well are qualified to govern the country. When they govern the country, they first consider implementing benevolent government and moral governance, and then seek peace and stability throughout the world. It can be said that this is the “Way of The Great Learning” hidden in the subconscious of Chinese scholars throughout history.

The concept of “harmony without uniformity,” which has been existent in ancient China, serves as a means to achieve the goals of self-cultivation, family regulation, state governance, and bringing peace to the world. *The Discourses of the States*, compiled around the turn of the Spring and Autumn and Warring States periods (around 476 BC), contains a chapter titled

“Discourses of Zheng,” which records a dialogue between Duke Huan and Shi Bo regarding “harmony without uniformity.” Duke Huan asked, “Will the Zhou Dynasty decline?” Shi Bo replied, “It is almost certain to decline.” Then, Shi Bo cited a statement from the Tai Shi of the Book of Shangshu, which states that “what the common people aspire to, Heaven will surely follow.” He believed that King You of Zhou dynasty had abandoned those who were upright, virtuous, and illuminated, and instead favoured those who sowed discord and were crafty and sinister. Most importantly, he preferred “rejecting harmony and choosing uniformity,” that is, excluding propositions that differed from his own but might be correct, and adopting views that were the same as his own but might be wrong. Only harmony can generate all things; uniformity cannot lead to development. Harmony means coordinating and balancing different things to achieve concord, thus enabling enrichment and development, ultimately unifying all things. If one always turns differences into sameness, merely adding together identical things, then once they are exhausted, there is nothing left. The five elements of metal, wood, water, fire, and earth combine to generate all things. Blending five flavors makes the food palatable. Harmonizing six musical notes makes the sounds pleasant to the ear. Rectifying the seven sense organs serves the heart. Coordinating the various parts of the body makes a person complete. Establishing the nine internal organs fosters pure virtue. Thus, thousands of grades are produced, tens of thousands of methods are available, billions of things are calculated, trillions of properties are managed, and hundreds of millions of revenues are obtained. Therefore, the monarch, possessing the vast land of the nine provinces, obtains revenues to support the common people, educates them with loyalty and faith, and makes them harmonious and happy like a family. This is the acme of harmony. A wise ruler selects those who dare to remonstrate directly to serve as officials, handles numerous affairs, and endeavors to achieve harmony rather than uniformity. A single sound cannot be melodious, a single colour cannot create a pattern, a single flavour cannot make a delicious dish, and a single thing cannot be measured, referenced, or compared. King You of Zhou abandoned this principle of harmony and specifically favoured uniformity, so the Zhou Dynasty could not but decline. In conclusion, the co-existence of differences is the basic law for the harmonious development of the world, which is an important source of the philosophical concept of “harmony without uniformity.” This philosophical concept evolved into two distinct ways of getting along among people in “The Analects of Confucius: Zilu.” “Confucius said, ‘The 君子(jun zi, as the English gentleman) aims at harmony but not at uniformity. The 小人(xiao ren, as the English petty man) aims at uniformity but not at harmony.’” The former belongs to the gentleman's character of pursuing “harmony without uniformity,” while the latter belongs to the petty man's character of pursuing “uniformity without harmony.” Confucius compared the gentleman with the petty man to highlight that the gentleman, who pursues “harmony without uniformity,” values righteousness. Although people with such a character may have different appearances, their inner aspirations are consistent. On the other hand, the petty man, who pursues “uniformity without harmony,” values profit. Although they may seem to be in agreement on the surface, they cannot truly get along harmoniously, and contention is their normal state.

China attaches great importance to the exchanges and mutual learning among different civilizations, advocates treating different cultures in the way of “harmony without uniformity,” and emphasizes the harmonious situation of mutual appreciation and co-creation among heterogeneous cultures. The greatest significance of Bakhtin's academic heritage to the Chinese people, apart from his restoration of the origins of the genre of the novel, also lies in his revelation of the characteristic of the “harmony without uniformity” in the novel. This characteristic strongly demonstrates that, as in China, there has been an “anti-uniform thinking tendency” or, as L.A. Gogotishvili in her paper *Variants and Invariants of M.M. Bakhtin* said,

“anti-monological thinking tendencies”[6]. In 1970 Bakhtin said, When there is a dialogue between two cultures, “each culture still maintains its own unity and **open** integrity, yet they enrich and fulfill each other” [2, vol. 6, p. 457]. Bakhtin's ideas about cross-cultural dialogue and the inter-subjectivity philosophical foundation of “I and the Other” resonate with the ancient Chinese philosophical thoughts from 2,500 years ago. This is probably an important reason why contemporary Chinese intellectuals unconsciously identify with Bakhtin.

3.

Despite the efforts of his friends to intercede for him, Mikhail Bakhtin ultimately could not escape the fate of a legal penalty — he was deported to southern Kazakhstan for six years of labor reform. On March 29, 1930, four days before he set off for the place of exile with his wife, he drew out the research plan for «Questions of Rhetoric in the Novel» [2, vol. 3, p. 6]. The plan was likely conceived in early June 1929, shortly after the publication of «Problems of Dostoevsky's Creation» [2, vol. 3, p. 713]. It was also at this time that Rabelais began to come into his academic considerations [9]. The above-mentioned plan was a blueprint for the study of the novel as a literary genre. In the following decade or so (1930 – 1941), Bakhtin's academic exploration basically did not deviate from this original design. He discovered the rhetorical line of the eloquent style, which was different from that of the epic – novel, and traced the origins of the novel genre that developed along this line – the folk comic culture. He sought evidence in Rabelais' novels and named it the folk carnival culture. This broadened the horizons and methods of genre study of the novel in terms of cultural roots, provided a theoretical basis for the origin of the German Bildungsroman and the Russian polyphonic novel in the folk festival culture, and ultimately laid the foundation for the establishment of his new paradigm for humanistic research.

In 1975, Bakhtin's first collection of essays, “Problems of Literature and Aesthetics”, was published. The book contains a total of six articles, among which there are four long essays. In sequence, they are “The Discourse of the Novel: On Questions of the Rhetoric of the Novel”, “The Temporal Forms and Chronotope Forms of the Novel: An Outline of Historical Poetics”, “The Genesis of the Novel's Discourse”, and “Epic and Novel: On the Methodology of Novel Studies”. These are powerful works dedicated to the study of the genre of the novel. In fact, all of them were written in the 1930s. In 1934 – 1935, Bakhtin completed a manuscript titled «The Discourse of the Novel», which primarily delved into two aspects: the genre of the novel and literary discourse. Subsequently, this manuscript was split into three papers: “The Discourse of Poetry and the Discourse of the Novel”, “The Origins of the Novel’s Discourse”, and “Epic and Novel”. These were successively published in the journal *Problems of Literature and the anthology Literature in Russia and Abroad* between 1965 and 1972. The main part of the essay on the chronotope was written in 1937 – 1938, and the “Conclusion” was added in 1973. The entire text was published in *Problems of Literature* in 1974 [1, pp. 4–5]. In 1981, American scholars compiled and published these four long essays in an English – language. Since then, «Bakhtin's novel theory» has become a specific term that has spread throughout the Western academic community. The third volume of the Russian-language Collected Works by M.M. Bakhtin published in 2012, based on the manuscript «The Discourse of the Novel», restored the original state of Bakhtin's study on novel theory from the 1930s to the early 1940s.

In Russia from the late 19th century to the early 20th century, the theoretical trend of thought that stood out the most prominently was the opposition to normative poetics and the pursuit of scientific poetics. In 1919, in his article «The Tasks of Poetics», V. M. Zhirmunsky stated, “In recent years the science of literature has been developing under the banner of poetics” [14, p. 15]. In his 1925 textbook *Theory of Literature: Poetics*, B. V. Tomashevsky

clearly pointed out that the task of poetics “is to study the various means of constructing literary works”, and its method “is to describe, classify various phenomena, and expound on these phenomena” [13, p. 22]. Like other formalists, he also made a distinction between “pure literature (poetry)” and “non-pure literature (prose/novel)”, believing that “the discipline that studies the structure of non-pure literary works is called rhetorics, and the discipline that studies the structure of pure literary works is called poetics. Rhetorics and poetics form the general theory of literature” [13, p. 25]. He divided poetics into historical poetics, which studies the origins of various literary devices, general poetics, which studies the functions of these devices, and normative poetics, which formulates the rules of literary creation. This textbook was praised as “a serious, clear, and substantial textbook”, “rare both in the past and today” [5, vol. Appendix 1, p. 16]. However, the practice of classifying novels into the category of “non-pure literature” and believing that they can only be studied by rhetoric was criticized by Bakhtin: “Since people couldn't find the expected pure poetic (in a narrow sense) forms in the novel's discourse, they denied that the novel's discourse had any artistic value; they claimed that like practical speech or scientific speech in life, it was just a non – artistic means of transmission” [2, vol. 3. p. 13]. He was deeply dissatisfied with the fact that “the style of the novel is mostly attributed to the ‘epic style’”, and that the novel was regarded as “a modern form of moral preaching... a non-artistic rhetorical genre” or “a mixture of rhetoric and pure poetry” [2, vol. 3, pp. 18, 20–21]. He believed that the so-called negative factors of the novel, such as having no clear boundaries, lacking stability, stylization, and clarity in genre, and lacking poetry in language, should actually be regarded as the advantages of the novel. Only in this way could one truly grasp the artistic characteristics of the novel genre. At that time, almost all Russian scholars interested in the novel inherited Hegel's tradition: the novel originated from the epic and was merely a mixture of the epic and drama. Many scholars even went further than their predecessors in belittling the novel and exalting the epic, with a more radical stance. Contrary to this popular tradition at that time, Bakhtin tried to start a new and find a new “foundation” for the novel, thus seeking a genre origin other than the epic for the novel. In the supplementary material “Questions of the Theory and History of the Novel” in 1943, he pointed out that the existing literary theory could not meet the needs of the study of the novel genre: «The novel has transformed European literary thinking. Literature, literary images, and literary discourse are no longer what they were before the novel became dominant. However, literary theory remains as it was (Aristotle – Horace – Boileau...). The novel should also transform the theoretical thinking about literature. The models of the world, of people, and of discourse themselves are different in the novel. Different, too, is the very basis of image construction» [2, vol. 3, p. 655].

For a long time both before and after Bakhtin wrote these words, the study of the novel had never broken free from the stereotype of its origin in the epic. He himself divided the novel genre into two “rhetorical lines”: “The first” belongs to the epic-eloquent style; “The second” was first proposed by him, and its origin was traced back to ancient folk comic culture. It is precisely the interweaving and mutual struggle of these two lines that jointly promoted the formation and continuous evolution of the novel genre.

4.

What strikes Chinese people the most in Bakhtin's works on novel theory is a series of new concepts. Some of them are his original coinages, truly “coining new terms”, such as novelization, internally persuasive discourse, alien discourse, dialogism, chronotope, double-voicedness, speech genre, etc. Others can be regarded as “old terms with new meanings”, like ambivalence of the positive – negative unity, hybridization, intonation, embedding, parody,

stylization, voice, non-direct speech, etc. It is precisely these new concepts that underpin the new paradigm for the study of novels. Bakhtin liked to use categories of contradictory opposition yet dialectical unity to expound on the particularity of the novel, elevating it to one of the originating genres on a par with the epic, lyric poetry, and drama, thus enhancing the distinctiveness of this genre.

Standard language (unified language, normative language, common language) – Heteroglossia; Centripetal force – Centrifugal force.

Heteroglossia is the most fascinating new discovery in Bakhtin's novel theory. Previous studies in linguistics and rhetoric often focused not on the whole of co-existing languages, but on the comparison between one language or several languages, as well as on how individuals use a certain language (most typically, the standard language) to create speech works. The standard language, that is, the officially recognized unified, normative, and common language, is a solid and stable core within the diverse dialects of a nation. Its formation is “the force that unifies and centralizes the world of discourse and thought” [2, vol. 3, p. 24], which is the result of the continuous action of centripetal force. The importance of centripetal force to the standard language and the importance of language unity to the formation of a nation and a country are self-evident. However, in the process of language unification, there is also a dispersive force, namely, centrifugal force. At every moment of its formation and development, language is not only divided into dialects as defined by linguistics, but also includes languages of different social consciousness, such as the languages of social groups, occupations, genres, genders, and generations. Together, they constitute heteroglossia. Thus, the normative language is just one type within heteroglossia, and it can be further divided into languages of different genres, schools, and functional styles within itself. As long as language survives and develops, the phenomenon of differentiation and heteroglossia will expand and deepen. In short, the struggle between centripetal force and centrifugal force creates a picture of a hubbub of voices. Heteroglossia is a true reflection of the centrifugal force of language and also reveals the real state of existence of human language.

Based on the above-mentioned view of language, Bakhtin compared the discourses of novels and poetry. He believed that the former is formed on the decentralized and centrifugal track of language and ideological life, while the latter develops on the centripetal track of cohesive and centralized ideology. In his opinion, the novel represents an image of heteroglossia, poetry represents an image of unified language, and the epic represents an image of the “absolute past”. Using the methods of studying the language of poetry and the epic to examine the novel cannot truly reveal the essential characteristics of its discursive art. Therefore, it is necessary to explore a new path and establish a unique methodology for novel research.

The first rhetorical route – The second rhetorical route; Epic – Novel; Finishedness – Unfinishedness.

Bakhtin traced two rhetorical routes in European novels. The first route originated from the eloquent narrative literature, and its basic feature is to maintain a certain degree of monolingualism and a uniform style. The second route consciously introduced social heteroglossia into creation. However, in their historical development, the novel following the first route gradually moved towards heteroglossia from top to bottom, while the novel following the second route “rose from the depths of heteroglossia, entered and mastered the high-level standard language” [2, vol. 3, p. 155] from bottom to top that is, they turned the elegant language into a component of heteroglossia. Bakhtin elaborated in detail on the relationship of mutual struggle and confrontation between the epic and the novel, which represent these two routes. Compared with the epic, the novel came into being much later and is the only genre in

the literary family that is still in the process of formation. The novel aims to depict the contemporary life of the author. Its images are open, incomplete in terms of meaning and value, and it has great freedom in form and content. The images of the epic are complete because it entirely belongs to the “absolute past”, that is, “there is an absolute epic distance” [2, vol. 3, p. 617] between the era of the epic author and the era, in which the epic events and characters are set. The art of the novel reveals the present existence oriented towards the future, while the epic presents the fixed and unchanging events of the past.

The epic, representing the first route, has a fixed and unchangeable creative stance. For example, sacred things must never be desecrated, and a feeling of reverence must be held towards heroic figures. The novel, which has developed along the second route, has completely liberated artistic thinking, making it possible for solemnity and laughter to transform into each other. The advantage of the novel also lies in “constantly changing all the forms it has taken shape” [2, vol.3, p. 641]. “Once it takes a dominant position in literary life, the whole system of genres has been changed (almost all other genres were novelized)” [2, vol. 3, p. 811]. Novelization essentially means adopting the creative stance of the novel. One creates with an unfinished and free stance. Whether it is the selection of character images, the arrangement of plot structures, the adoption of language styles, the description of scenes, or the expression of ideas, one consciously breaks free from the constraints of established genre frameworks. The polyphonic novel is a genre that has developed along the second route. Its artistic world lacks the epic – like completeness because the author endows the protagonist with the right to speak about the world and himself. For the novel that has developed along the first route, that is, the monologic novel as Bakhtin called it, the privilege of speaking about the world and the protagonist himself belongs to the author.

Descriptive discourse – Described discourse; The language consciousness of the describer – The language consciousness of the described.

The images in the novel are all depicted through language. In short, they are images of discourse. In the eyes of the novelist, any object is not an objective thing, but a “linguisticized” reality, consisting of various names, concepts, evaluations, etc. in the social heteroglossic world. The novel not only depicts real life but also serves as a unique stage for the intersection and dialogue of different languages. Most of the languages that enter the novel are not completely individualized. The author, the protagonist, and their unique voices seem to be immersed in the ocean of social heteroglossia. Therefore, the novel, as a whole, is a reflection of the language reality of the time. It is “a multi-stylistic, heteroglossic, and polyphonic phenomenon”, “a socially heteroglossic phenomenon organized by artistic means, occasionally a multilingual one, and also a unique polyphonic phenomenon of the individual” [2, vol. 3, p. 14]. In other words, it is a microcosm of the dialogized heteroglossic world. This world endows language with a special function in the aesthetic activities of the novel: it may no longer be a simple means of expression for referring to things and stating events; instead, the language itself often becomes the object of description. “The image of language as a deliberately created hybrid” “has two language consciousnesses: one is the language consciousness of the described, and the other is the language consciousness of the describer belonging to another language system” [2, vol. 3, p. 114]. Without the first consciousness, what the reader faces is not a literary work but a practical text, and its language directly refers to things and states events. Without the second consciousness, what the reader sees is not an image of language but “a sample of someone else’s language” (ibid.). To create images in the novel, two language consciousnesses are often required. “One language consciousness is reflected by the other”, or in other words, “it must be from the perspective of another language (the generally recognized normative language)” (ibid.). One of the important methods for creating the language image of a novel is

“the hybridization of language”. The deliberate hybridization is not only marked by certain linguistic forms but also possesses semantic value, such as the interweaving of two worldviews or two intentions and viewpoints represented by two social languages. In the historical development of the natural language, the natural hybridization itself will give rise to new worldviews.

Skilled writers are adept at transforming the language in their works into a form that both describes and is being described simultaneously, which fully manifests the mutual reflection between the language consciousness of the describing and that of the being described. Let's take an example to illustrate this. Lu Xun's *A Madman's Diary* was a pioneer of vernacular novels during the May 4th Movement. However, at the beginning, there is a short preface in classical Chinese. Why? At that time, during the formative years of stylistic innovation in literature, the mixture of classical and vernacular Chinese was not uncommon as a transitional form. Generally, it was just a personal writing style of the writer and might not imply other intentions. But Lu Xun was different. The narrator employs classical Chinese discourse to explain the matter (“one language consciousness”, that is, the character’s consciousness of classical Chinese), and within the overall framework of the novel (“another language consciousness”, that is, the author’s consciousness of vernacular Chinese), this discourse and the speaker behind it seem to be “put on display” for readers to observe, compare, and even mock. The narrator uses classical Chinese to explain the origin and development of the diary, while the author, through the classical Chinese style, reveals the narrator's dull, pedantic, and self – conceited image. From the perspective of the internal dialogism of the discourse, the preface clearly belongs to parodic (mimicking) discourse. The author imitates the classical Chinese style with a satirical intention towards the narrator's consciousness of classical Chinese. And the discourse in the diary, which is the main text, belongs to stylized discourse. The author imitates the vernacular style of the madman and forms an «alliance» with this style to resist and subvert the image of the feudal orthodoxy, which is the protagonist hidden in the readers' consciousness. When the describing and being described merge into one within the same discourse, it triggers a “chemical reaction” in the language, a phenomenon worth further exploitation. Unfortunately, its significance to literary creation has not yet received due recognition, and its theoretical potential has not been deeply explored.

In his monograph on Dostoevsky, Bakhtin mainly explored various dialogical relationships between the author and the protagonist. By the 1930s, he shifted his focus from character images to language images, and thus from the exploration of existence to the field of language. This led to the emergence of a topic frequently discussed in post-modern philosophy: regarding existence as a problem of language reality.

Solemnity (seriousness, loftiness) – Laughter (wittiness).

Where exactly lies the genre origin of the novel discourse developed from the second rhetorical route? The answer to this question constitutes the core of Bakhtin's methodology for the study of the novel. This origin is the folk comic culture. The key to Bakhtin's discovery of this fact is the category of chronotope that he borrowed from A. A. Ukhtomsky. This category not only functions in the layout of the plot (pure layout form), but also plays a role in determining the plot and character images (constructive form). It is a category that combines form and content, reflecting the clear thread of Bakhtin's academic pursuit during this period. It has a two-fold theoretical significance: there are many large and small chronotopes within the artistic world of the work, and they are in various dialogical relationships; the communication between the work and real life is achieved through the chronotope. In the process of the writer's creation and the reader's reception, the collisions and dialogues between the chronotope of the artistic world and the real-life chronotopes of the writer and the reader all

illustrate the complexity and particularity of the chronotope, which originates outside art, acts on the artistic world, and transcends the artistic world. Therefore, the chronotope is widely recognized as a cultural category with great academic potential. However, for Bakhtin, it was initially just a theoretical instrument for exploring the evolution of the novel genre. With this, he discovered the uniqueness in the creation of Rabelais' novels and first proposed "Rabelaisian laughter" [2, vol. 3, pp. 421, 484], believing that *Gargantua and Pantagruel* is a typical representative whose origins of genre lie in the folk comic culture.

The folk comic culture is a significant discovery when Bakhtin constructed his novel theory, playing a specific role of continuing the polyphonic novel theory before and paving the way for the carnivalization theory after. Bakhtin first presented his discovery of the folk comic culture in his article on chronotope, and then immediately wrote "Rabelais in the History of Realism", which made the novels of the second rhetorical route run through from their pre-historical discourse to modern discourse. Eventually, it provided a solid theoretical foundation for Bakhtin to formulate the research methodology for the study of the novel.

5.

The above-mentioned new concepts also reflect the characteristics of Bakhtin's philosophical thinking after the 1920s: the integration of philosophy and philology (literary studies/linguistics), as explained by V. V. Kozhinov, "Any 'philological-sense' judgment in Bakhtin's works is also, and to the same extent, a 'philosophical-sense' one" [7, p. 122]. Galin Tihanov believes that Bakhtin's study on the novel and its theory goes beyond literature itself, forming a unique cultural philosophy [12, chapter 3]. The integration of philosophy and philology can be verified by Bakhtin's short essay "On the Philosophical Foundations of the Humanities", written between 1941 and 1943. This essay is actually a "philosophical" continuation of his novel theory. As suggested by the text in the caption, the manuscript is clearly divided into two parts. The first part expounds on the epistemological issues of the humanities, and the second part, combined with the study of Rabelais, discusses "seriousness" and its relationship with laughter, which can also be attributed to epistemological issues. This also means that Bakhtin has taken a solid step from the research methodology of the novel to the research methodology of the humanities as a whole.

In "Problems of Dostoevsky's Creation", which was written and revised over a period of ten years and published in 1929, Bakhtin pointed out that the path of philosophical monologization is the basic path of literary criticism on Dostoevsky, and Relevant scholars all regarded Dostoevsky's artistic world as a framework of a monologue system dominated by a unified worldview [2, vol. 2, pp. 14–16]. However, in Bakhtin's view, this is not the case:

«All elements of the structure of the novel acquire profound uniqueness in Dostoevsky's works. All these elements depend on a new artistic task, which only Dostoevsky could put forward and address with great breadth and depth. This task is to create a polyphonic world and break the established forms of European novels, which are basically m o n o l o g i c (single-melody)» [2, vol. 2, p. 13].

The polyphonic novel, a new type of novel centered around the artistic thinking of dialogue, serves as a powerful counterforce against the "philosophical path of monologization". This constitutes the primary internal impetus for Bakhtin's unhesitating transition from the realm of philosophy – aesthetics to the field of philology. In brief, with the aim of delving into the genre origin of the polyphonic novel, Bakhtin embarked on a decade – long exploration of the artistry of the novel. He unearthed the folk comic culture and its "literary carnivalization" tendency, thereby giving rise to two complementary thinking trends within his theoretical framework: dialogue and carnival, both of which subvert the monologic thinking tendency.

Evidently, the ingenious construction of Bakhtin's novel theory conceals his discontent with the European culture dominated by monologic thinking, along with his unwavering pursuit of the diametrically – opposed thinking tendency.

Bakhtin constructed a novel theory with the form of poetics but the essence of philosophy. Among them, the relationship between the monologic and anti-monologic thinking tendencies is a hidden yet most fascinating feature. L.A. Gogotishvili elaborated in detail on the interaction between several monologic thinking tendencies and the anti-monologic thinking tendency composed of dialogue and carnival when interpreting M.M. Bakhtin. This can accurately illustrate the Russian thinker's lifelong academic pursuit, and the result of this pursuit is enough to trigger a “Copernican revolution”.

Bakhtin initiated a new paradigm for humanistic studies, the “thinking system of monologism and anti-monologism”, and through his study of the novel, he created many new categories to support this new paradigm. He used pairs of concepts that are easy to understand and even common in daily life. Besides those listed above, there are also “monologue – dialogue”, “monologism – dialogism”, “monologic novel – polyphonic novel”, “sentence – discourse”, “direct speech- non-direct speech”, “poetic – novelistic”, etc. There are also “official culture – folk culture” which describes the world perception of the “carnival”, and its richly connotative extended concepts such as “carnivalization”, “literary carnivalization”, “carnivalization of consciousness”, “carnivalization of routine life”. In order to expound the characteristics of the anti-monologic cultural thinking tendency composed of a series of categories such as “dialogue – carnival – novel – discourse – heteroglossia – centrifugal force – incompleteness – laughter”, and also to clarify the particularity of the novel genre, Bakhtin also adopted concepts such as event, action, duality, speech genre, novelization, chronotope, hybridization, intonation, inlay, parody, voice, polyphony, and the other’s discourse (chuzhoe slovo). All the above-mentioned terms have been endowed with unique connotations within the context of Bakhtin's academic legacy. The vast majority of them have been adopted by scholars of literary and cultural studies. Russian scholars have even specifically compiled and published *The Bakhtin Lexical Repository* [11] to explain in detail this whole set of terms and their internal relationships, an endeavor that, regrettably, the international philosophical community has been very lukewarm about. The reason, after all, is that Bakhtin’s conceptual system is incompatible with the current philosophical paradigm, and thus fails to gain the general recognition of the philosophical community.

When examining Bakhtin's novel theory, it is difficult to understand why he was so enthusiastic about exploring the anti-monologic thinking tendency derived from concepts of dialogue and carnival in the history of European culture, if we fail to recognize the historical background in which his theory came into being and was discovered. It is hard to gain a fuller understanding of the internal logic of Bakhtin’s conceptual system that combines the form of poetics with the essence of philosophy without delving into the personal history of his academic development. And it is nearly impossible to truly comprehend his revolutionary new paradigm for humanities research without a deep-going elaboration of his unique “lexical repository”. In short, Bakhtin's study of the theory of the novel, serving as a subtle camouflage of his reflections on the relationship between monologic and anti-monologic thinking, is something truly worth further contemplations by Bakhtinian scholars.

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